

Modeling and Forecasting of Time Series Data using Different Techniques

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Abstract

Currency is an important economic indicator. The indicator has some significant impact on the development of a country. A few key models have been suggested to improve the accuracy and efficiency of modeling and predict time series. This study examines the effects of currency exchange rate under Random Walk Model, Single Exponential Smoothing, Double Exponential Smoothing and Holt-Winter Models and the forecasting performances of the models are judged by the measure of accuracy both symmetric and asymmetric loss functions are used Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE). From the measure of accuracy, double exponential smoothing model can be used to predict and smoothing the series of currency exchange rate with the other three different model. By comparing several models with the smallest value of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), we assessed an Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model that could be used to predict the exchange rate of the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC).

Introduction

In making financial related decision, researchers very often use econometric or time series model. Econometric model assumes stationary in the series but time series data are mostly non-stationary. Forecasting a series of financial periods such as currency exchange rates are important for investors and position the government. Good financial forecasts the series requires a strong background and good knowledge analytical tools (Leu et al., 2006). Rates are naturally sound, stable, and well-aligned with decisions (G. Deboeck et al., 1994, S. Yaser & A. Atiya, 1996). If the data is not fixed there is a problem that arises as a problem of spurious regression. If lag dependent variable is present in the model then our first task is to check stationary. So our main aim is to develop model for the currency exchange rate data of SAARC countries with lag, then check stationary by using unit root test with appropriate critical values and check whether they are integrated or not. To test for a unit root, the method employed was that of Dickey-Fuller (Dickey et al., 1979). Unit root testing is one of the most well-known methods used by researchers to determine whether a stochastic process is stationary or not and if stationary, at what order. According to Engle and Granger (1987), if two random walk series have a long-term equilibrium relationship, they cannot be separated indefinitely. The deviation from their long-term equilibrium relationship should be constant with zero mean. In this case, the two price series are said to be cointegrated. Naik and Padhi (2012) find that macroeconomic variables and the stock market index (BSE Sensex) are co-integrated and thus a long-run equilibrium relationship exists between them in the India stock market. They find a positive relationship between stocks prices and money supply, and industrial production, but a negative relationship for inflation. Hashimoto and Ito (2004) also attempt such study on the eight countries in the region during the period of Asian currency crisis, 1997-1999 and considered two variables-exchange rate and stock price. The researchers of both studies believe that the sharp depreciation of the Thai baht causes depreciation of other currencies in the region which in turn contributes to the collapse of the stock markets of that region. Muhammad and Rasheed (Muhammad et al., 2002) studied the relationship between stock prices and exchange rates for four South Asian countries. No significant relationship between the variables is found for the country of India and Pakistan but a bidirectional relationship is found for the country of Bangladesh and Srilanka. Similar study has been conducted by Rahman and Uddin (Rahman et al., 2009.) for three Asian countries named as Bangladesh, India and Pakistan. Their study shows no causal relationship between stock prices and exchange rates in the countries. The study of Ahmad et al. (2010) examines the relationship between stock return, interest rate and exchange rates in Pakistani economy. They conclude that the change in interest rate has a negative while change in exchange rate has a positive impact on stock return.

To check randomness and stationary by using nonparametric and parametric tests. Also investigate the long run relationship between two SAARC countries currency exchange rate by co-integration analysis. To examine the volatile conditions of each rate by considering ARCH effect in the random errors of Econometric transforms

model. The main objectives of the paper are develop time series models and to determine the best model for forecasting the data by measuring error of the currency exchange rate of the SAARC countries. Finally, applying lowest AIC criteria to select best model, (Thomas Lumley et al., 2004) forecast the currency exchange rate data of SAARC countries.

Methodology

For the purpose of analysis, we collect data of currency exchange rate of SAARC countries which are converted from USD from the year of 1996 to 2016. At first, the stationary status has been check by using the time plot of the series, correlogram, randomness checking and unit root test. Then find whether the series of SAARC countries are cointegrated or not and also find the co-integration between the series of two SAARC countries. Another task is to check the volatility. If volatility exists, we look at whether the ARCH effect is present or not. In order to investigate the main objectives of this paper, we use a variety of time series methods such as the Time Series Plot, different smoothing techniques, different non-stationary tests, the ARCH model of instability and other complex mathematical processes. Several methods were developed to predict and compare with the ARIMA model. Model performance is measured with a mean percentage error (MAPE), root mean square error (RMSE), and mean square error (MAE) (Hanke et al., 2005). For more than two decades in the Box and Jenkins' The Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) technologies, G. E. P. Box and G. M. Jenkins and widely used in a time series of prediction. Due to its popularity, the ARIMA model was used as a test guide for some of the modeling methods (H. B. Hwang & H. T. Ang, 2002). Weisang et al. (2014) also developed a detailed ARIMA model in the form of case studies using macroeconomic indicators to model the exchange rate of USD / EUR. They developed an equitable exchange rate of the USD / EUR monthly exchange rate for the period from January 1994 to October 2007. Akincilar et al. (2011) studied the forecast for the exchange rate of the US dollar, the euro, and the Great Britain pound against the Turkish lira. However, ARIMA is one of the most inconsistent models and is based on the assumption that the timeline is unstructured, i.e., linear and stationary (L. Cao & F. Tay, 2001).

Results and Discussion

The first step in the analysis of any time series is to plot the data. Such a plot gives an initial clue about the likely nature of the time series or shows an upward or downward trend, seasonal or cyclical variations etc.

Time series plot

Figure 1: Time Series Plot of Currency Exchange Rate of (a) Bangladesh, (b) Srilanka, (c) Afghanistan, and (d) India

Figure 2: Time Series Plot of Currency Exchange Rate of (a) Pakistan , (b) Bhutan , (c) Nepal, and (d) Maldives In Fig. 1 (a), (b) we can see that currency exchange rate of Bangladesh and Srilanka follows upward trend. In Fig. 1 (c), (d) and Fig 2 we can see that currency exchange rate of Afghanistan, India, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan and Maldives follows upward and downward trend. So the currency exchange rate of all SAARC countries are non-stationary.

Correlogram Test (Graphical analysis)

Figure 3: Autocorrelation function (a, c) and Partial autocorrelation function (b, d) of currency exchange rate of Bangladesh and Afghanistan

Figure 4: Autocorrelation function (a, c) and Partial autocorrelation function (b, d) of currency exchange rate of India and Pakistan.

Figure 5: Autocorrelation function (a, c) and Partial autocorrelation function (b, d) of currency exchange rate of Sri Lanka and Bhutan

Figure 6: Autocorrelation function (a, c) and Partial autocorrelation function (b, d) of currency exchange rate of Nepal and Maldives

From the Figs. 3, 4, 5, and 6, we find that the most striking feature of this coupling is that the self-correction coefficient of different lags and the partial self-correction coefficient are very high. Thus, we conclude that the time series of currency exchange rate of SAARC is non-stationary.

Unit Root Test

Unit Root Test for Different Countries of Currency Exchange Rate where H_0 : The series of currency exchange rate of different SAARC Countries are non-stationary and H_1 : The series of currency exchange rate of different SAARC Countries are stationary.

Table 1: Unit Root Test for Different Countries of Currency Exchange Rate

Currency Name	Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Decision
Afghani	-4.335965	-3.029970	Rejected
Indian Rupee	-5.919998	-3.029970	Rejected
Pakistani Rupee	-20.99676	-3.029970	Rejected
Sri Lankan Rupee	-5.382531	-3.029970	Rejected
Ngultrum	-5.361040	-3.029970	Rejected
Nepalese Rupee	-5.303467	-3.029970	Rejected
Maldivian Rufiyaa	-4.595926	-3.029970	Rejected

From the Table 1, we can see that the calculated value is greater than the tabulated value at 5% level of significance for all the currencies of SAARC countries. So we conclude that the series of currencies of SAARC countries is stationary.

Co-integration test between the currency exchange rate of different countries where H_0 : The series of currency exchange rate of two countries are not co-integrated and H_1 : The series of currency exchange rate of two countries are co-integrated.

Table 2: Co-integration test between the currency exchange rate

Currency Name	Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Decision
AFN VS LKR	-1.24272.	-3.00	not rejected
BTN VS LKR	-1.71202	-3.00	not rejected
INR VS LKR	-1.88108	-3.00	not rejected
MVR VS LKR	-2.32412	-3.00	not rejected
AFN VS BTN	-0.64193.	-3.00	not rejected

From table 2, the calculated value is less than the set value, we accept the null hypothesis at a value level of 5%. Thus, we may conclude that the currency exchange rate of Afghanistan and Sri Lanka are not co-integrated.

Volatility Test

Volatility Measuring by ARCH Effect where H_0 = There is no ARCH effect in the series of currency exchange rate of SAARC Countries and H_1 = There is an ARCH effect in the series of currency exchange rate of SAARC Countries.

Table 3: Volatility Measuring by ARCH Effect

Currency Name	Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Decision
Afghani	0.053775	0.8194	not rejected
Indian Rupee	0.013814	0.9078	not rejected
Pakistani Rupee	0.125294	0.7280	not rejected
Sri Lankan Rupee	0.215234	0.8054	not rejected
Ngultrum	0.312512	0.7243	not rejected
Nepalese Rupee	0.391155	0.5405	not rejected
Maldivian Rufiyaa	0.112446	0.7415	not rejected

From the above Table 3, we can see that the calculated value is less than the tabulated value for all the currencies of SAARC countries. So the null hypothesis is accepted. Since the null hypothesis is accepted, so there is no ARCH effect in the series of currencies of SAARC countries. Thus we may conclude that the volatility is absent in the time series of currency exchange rate of SAARC countries, which indicates that the variance of the time series are not varied.

Table 4: Estimation Period for the Currency Exchange Rate of Different SAARC Countries

Country	Model	AIC	Country	Model	AIC
Bangladesh	ARIMA (2,1,1)	1.88033	Sri Lanka	ARIMA (0,2,1)	3.37689
	ARIMA (0,1,0)	1.88373		ARIMA (0,1,0)	3.4433
	ARIMA (0,1,2)	1.8952		ARIMA (1,0,0)	3.46606
	ARIMA (1,0,0)	1.96431		ARIMA (0,2,2)	3.48537
	ARIMA (2,1,2)	1.9781		ARIMA (0,1,1)	3.52356
Afghanistan	ARIMA (0,1,1)	13.9081	Bhutan	ARIMA (0,2,2)	2.50598
	ARIMA (1,0,0)	13.9086		ARIMA (1,1,2)	2.54862
	ARIMA (0,1,0)	14.0033		ARIMA (0,1,2)	2.55474
	ARIMA (0,1,2)	14.0546		ARIMA (1,1,2)	2.60046
	ARIMA (1,1,2)	14.0778		ARIMA (0,2,2)	2.65314
India	ARIMA (0,1,2)	2.37263	Nepal	ARIMA (1,1,2)	3.2436
	ARIMA (0,2,2)	2.42602		ARIMA (1,2,2)	3.30671
	ARIMA (1,1,2)	2.47592		ARIMA (0,2,2)	3.39685
	ARIMA (1,2,2)	2.57035		ARIMA (1,2,2)	3.40151
	ARIMA (0,2,2)	2.58244		ARIMA (2,2,2)	3.41271
Pakistan	ARIMA (0,2,1)	5.10956	Maldives	ARIMA (0,1,2)	-0.912075
	ARIMA (1,0,2)	5.30872		ARIMA (0,1,0)	-0.894861
	ARIMA (0,2,2)	5.42182		ARIMA (1,0,0)	-0.868476
	ARIMA (2,0,2)	5.44851		ARIMA (0,2,1)	-0.867983
	ARIMA (0,2,2)	5.52954		ARIMA (0,1,2)	-0.836127

From the Table 4, compares the results of fitting different models to the data. The model with the lowest value of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is model, which has been used to generate the forecasts.

Table 5: Forecasting Currency Exchange Rate of SARRAC Countries

Country	Forecast Year	Forecast Value	95% Limits	
			Upper	Lower
Bangladesh	2017	80.2733	75.1747	85.3718
	2018	82.0128	74.3491	89.6765
	2019	83.8634	74.6117	93.1151
	2020	85.6290	74.8167	96.4412

	2021	87.4596	75.4270	99.4922
Afghanistan	2017	-183.56	-2290.06	1922.94
	2018	-419.18	-3312.98	2474.61
	2019	-654.81	-4163.47	2853.85
	2020	-890.43	-4921.24	3140.37
	2021	-1126.06	-5618.73	3366.61
India	2017	69.4135	63.5710	75.2559
	2018	69.5649	63.3375	75.7923
	2019	71.1350	61.5416	80.7284
	2020	72.7051	60.6516	84.7585
	2021	74.2751	60.1848	88.3655
Pakistan	2017	113.563	88.731	138.395
	2018	123.909	88.494	159.324
	2019	135.544	91.805	179.283
	2020	148.469	97.541	199.397
	2021	162.685	105.272	220.097
Sri Lanka	2017	153.046	142.432	163.660
	2018	158.840	143.326	174.354
	2019	164.762	145.138	184.386
	2020	170.811	147.426	194.197
	2021	176.989	150.027	203.951
Bhutan	2017	70.3533	62.6360	78.0706
	2018	72.7626	62.5885	82.9368
	2019	75.2523	62.9163	87.5882
	2020	77.8221	63.4770	92.1673
	2021	80.4723	64.2067	96.7380
Nepal	2017	108.857	97.713	120.001
	2018	112.490	97.626	127.354
	2019	114.111	96.844	131.377
	2020	117.417	97.629	137.205
	2021	119.311	97.603	141.020
Maldives	2017	15.3076	14.1076	16.5076
	2018	15.5353	14.1965	16.8741
	2019	15.7341	14.3931	17.0750
	2020	15.9328	14.5898	17.2759
	2021	16.1316	14.7864	17.4768

Table 6: Measures of Forecast Accuracy under Different Models for Currency Exchange Rate of Different Countries

Country	Model	Measures of Forecast Accuracy		
		MAPE	MAD	MSE
Bangladesh	Random Walk Model	2.99915	1.93650	5.83962
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	3.12668	1.98670	7.32034
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	2.52047	1.66485	5.68662
	Holt Winters' Model	3.7326	2.4738	10.7960
Afghanistan	Random Walk Model	1522	1088	1629798
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	528	232	1044742
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	698	340	1026024
	Holt Winters' Model	1843	1385	2666226
India	Random Walk Model	8.2679	4.0039	22.6938
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	5.8339	2.8801	15.4379
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	5.1358	2.4985	12.3498
	Holt Winters' Model	10.5835	5.2	39.2030

Pakistan	Random Walk Model	17.598	13.649	500.758
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	19.681	12.534	522.047
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	21.273	16.042	914.866
	Holt Winters' Model	51.17	34.76	1475.32
Sri Lanka	Random Walk Model	4.53304	4.3089	27.5001
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	5.0730	5.0761	38.6901
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	4.4120	4.3582	28.5110
	Holt Winters' Model	5.8105	6.0670	51.6527
Bhutan	Random Walk Model	8.3798	4.0712	23.5722
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	5.3452	2.6470	14.5020
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	5.8410	2.7436	13.0816
	Holt Winters' Model	11.0672	5.4586	43.7521
Nepal	Random Walk Model	8.3669	6.3752	56.4699
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	4.8023	3.8019	32.4874
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	5.5623	4.0945	30.4840
	Holt Winters' Model	10.3845	8.0822	96.8607
Maldives	Random Walk Model	3.90627	0.51101	0.38889
	Single Exponential Smoothing Model	1.86309	0.25598	0.40178
	Double Exponential Smoothing Model	2.40744	0.32347	0.40178
	Holt Winters' Model	3.82658	0.53115	0.61112

From the Table 6, we see that on the basis of all measure, the maximum model of currency rate where MAD, MSE and MAPE are the smallest for the double exponential smoothing model than the other model. So double exponential smoothing model can be used to predict and smoothing the series of currency exchange rate with the other three competitors model.

Conclusion

There are various methods to forecast time series data for the future periods but these are not appropriate for forecasting if the time series data are non-stationary. In this paper, the model with the lowest value of the Akaike Information Criterion which has been used to generate the forecasts. We tested the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model to forecast exchange rates. These studies outlined that the ARIMA model is comparatively accurate model to forecast the exchange rate.

Also measure of forecast accuracy under four models for the Currency Exchange Rate of SAARC countries. There are models used in the study are random walk model, single exponential smoothing, double exponential smoothing and Holt winter's method. By using above this model, we forecast the currency exchange rate of SAARC countries and comparing the above model on the basis on MAPE, MAD and MSE. On the basis of all measure, we see that the maximum model of currency exchange rate where MAD, MSE and MAPE are the smallest for the double exponential smoothing model than the other model.

Recommendation

According to forecasting results of this research, SAARC countries of currency rate increase continuously For investors, the above results do suggest that there is no way to hedge against a deterioration of financial conditions in any area during a crisis time. In future work, it would be useful to further investigate the link between international financial linkages and currency exchange rate behavior.

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